

AN EXAMINATION OF LMS INTEGRATION FOR 21ST-CENTURY COMPETENCIES IN A ZIMBABWEAN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Despite that the COVID-19 pandemic has made the virtual classroom the most viable option for meeting the educational needs of most students, some higher education institutions in Zimbabwe have been found wanting in this regard. The institutional learning management system (LMS) played a crucial role in guaranteeing uninterrupted learning and student engagement during the widespread shift towards online form of curriculum delivery brought on by the pandemic. LMS integration has become a key focus for 21st-century education, as higher education institutions look to prepare students for the workplace of the future. This study examined the use of a learning management system (LMS) in a Zimbabwean university, with the aim of assessing its impact on the development of 21st-century competencies. The study adopted a qualitative methodology where in-depth interviews were conducted as part of this exploratory study with 7 purposively selected lecturers, 5 technicians, and 10 randomly selected students at a Zimbabwean higher education institution of Technology. The findings suggest that the integration of the LMS into the curriculum has had a positive impact on student learning engagement. Findings also revealed that student's motivation is increased. A significant number of students also reported that the LMS can be challenging to use. The majority of lecturers felt that the LMS has improved their lesson delivery and tracking and assessing students' progress has been made easier. Recommendations suggest lecturers to be professionally developed and be trained with their students on LMS use, adequate technical support, the proper policy framework for LMS use, and upgrading of the LMS regularly keeping abreast with the evolving technology.

Keywords: Learning management systems, 21st-century skills, technology integration, higher education, blended learning, education policy, digital literacy.

1 INTRODUCTION

The 21st century has brought with it a new set of challenges for education, as the demands of the workforce and society have shifted. In order to prepare students for this new landscape, many higher education institutions have turned to technology-enhanced learning as a solution. One such technology is the learning management system (LMS), which provides a platform for the delivery of course materials, assessment, and communication. However, there is limited research on the effectiveness of LMS integration in developing 21st-century competencies in the context of higher education in developing countries like Zimbabwe. A study by Sanganyado & Nkomo (2018); and Nurkhin & Rohman (2023) found that the use of LMS in a Zimbabwean university improved student engagement and critical thinking skills. The use of learning management systems (LMS) in higher education in Zimbabwe has become increasingly popular in recent

years (Amankwah et al. 2022 & Prinsloo, P. & Kaliisa, R. (2022)). This shift has been driven by the need to prepare students for the 21st-century workplace, which requires a range of skills and competencies that go beyond the traditional academic curriculum. The research on LMS integration for 21st-century competencies in Zimbabwean higher education has focused on several key areas. These include the use of LMS to support: collaborative learning and the development of social and interpersonal skills; the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills; the development of digital literacy and information literacy skills, the development of creativity and innovation skills and the development of self-directed and lifelong learning skills. The research has also explored the challenges and opportunities associated with LMS integration in Zimbabwean higher education. These include access to technology reliable internet connectivity and lecturer training and support. This study was guided by the following questions:

1. Which LMSs are you using in teaching and learning?
2. How are the technicians and lecturers of assistance in the technical support in integrating the LMSs?
3. What challenges are faced by the students, lecturers, and technicians in the integration of LMSs?
4. What are the 21st-century competencies relevant to Higher Education?
5. How best do you think LMSs can be integrated?

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The TAM posits that the perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology are key determinants of acceptance and use (Sungur Gül, & Ateş 2023). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a framework that can be used to examine the factors that influence users' acceptance and use of technology. The model suggests that there are two main factors that influence technology acceptance: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. In the context of LMS integration in Zimbabwean higher education, the TAM framework can be used to understand the factors that influence students' acceptance and use of LMS. The model suggests that students are more likely to use an LMS if they perceive it to be useful and easy to use.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the literature on LMS integration for 21st-century competencies in Zimbabwean higher education would include an examination of existing research on the topic. This could include studies on the use of LMS in other countries and the factors that influence their use. The review also explores the current state of LMS use in Zimbabwe, the barriers to integration, and the benefits of LMS use for teaching and learning. A review of the literature could also include a discussion of the 21st-century competencies that are relevant to the context of Zimbabwean higher education.

3.1. Types of LMSS Used in Teaching and Learning

There are a number of different types of learning management systems (LMS) that are used in the 21st century. These include: Open-source LMSs, Commercial LMSs and Cloud-based LMS (Dobre 2015; Shdaifat & Obeidallah 2019). Open-source learning management systems (LMS) are software applications that are free to use and can be modified and distributed under an open-source license (Dobre 2015; Van de Heyde, Siebrits 2019; Chaubey & Bhattacharya 2015). This means that anyone can access the source code of the software and make changes to it. Open-source LMSs are typically developed by a community of volunteers, and they are often considered to be more flexible and customizable than commercial LMSs. Some popular open-source LMSs include Moodle, Sakai, and Open edX. Open-source LMSs can be a good option for institutions that have the resources to customize and maintain the software themselves. These are some of the most commonly used LMS platforms in higher education. Each platform has its own unique features and benefits, and the choice of platform will depend on the needs and preferences of the university and its students (Badaru & Adu 2022; Megalou et al. 2022).

Commercial learning management systems (LMS) are software applications that are developed and maintained by a commercial company (Dobre 2015; Van de Heyde, Siebrits 2019; Chaubey & Bhattacharya 2015). They are typically purchased by educational institutions through a subscription model. Some popular commercial LMSs include Blackboard, Canvas, and D2L Brightspace (Dobre 2015; Chaubey & Bhattacharya 2015). Commercial LMSs offer a number of advantages, including: A wide range of features and functionality; technical support and training from the vendor; guaranteed uptime and security. However, they can also be more expensive than open-source LMSs.

Cloud-based learning management systems (LMS) are software applications that are hosted on the cloud,

rather than on local servers (Dobre 2015; Chaubey & Bhattacharya 2015). This means that the software can be accessed from any device with an internet connection, rather than being tied to a specific computer or network. Some popular cloud-based LMSs include Google Classroom, Schoology, and Edmodo. The main advantage of cloud-based LMSs is their flexibility and accessibility. They are easy to set up and maintain, and they can be accessed from anywhere with an internet connection (Chatterjee et al. 2022).

3.2. Integration of LMS for Curriculum Delivery in Higher Education Institutions

In recent years, there has been an increasing trend of integrating learning management systems (LMS) into the curriculum delivery process in higher education institutions. This is done in order to create a more seamless and integrated learning experience for students. LMSs allow for the delivery of course materials, communication with instructors and peers, and assessment of student progress, all within a single platform (Gyau & Semarco 2023; Slobodian 2021). Future of Online and Digital Learning in Post-Secondary Art Institutions.). This can lead to improved student engagement and learning outcomes. While there are many benefits to this approach, there are also some challenges that need to be addressed. Integration of an LMS into the curriculum delivery process in universities typically involves several key steps. These include:

- Evaluating the current curriculum and identifying opportunities for technology-enhanced learning.
- Developing a plan for integrating the LMS into the curriculum.
- Training faculty and students on the use of the LMS.
- Piloting the LMS in a small group of courses or students.
- Evaluating the effectiveness of the LMS integration and making adjustments as needed.

3.3 Challenges of LMS Use by Lecturers, Students, and Technicians in Higher Education Institutions

There are a number of challenges that have been identified in the use of learning management systems (LMS) in higher education (Pietersen 2023). In the United States and China, there are several challenges to the use of learning management systems (LMS) (Gamede et al 2022; Prahani, et al. 2022). One challenge is the diversity of the student population, which can make it difficult to find a single LMS that meets the needs of all students. Additionally, both countries have large populations, which can make it difficult to ensure that all students have access to the same resources and support. Another challenge is the high cost of implementing and maintaining an LMS, which can be a barrier for some institutions. Finally, both countries have different cultural and educational traditions, which can impact the effectiveness of LMS use. To address these challenges, institutions in the United States and China have taken a variety of approaches. For example, many institutions have invested in creating or adapting LMSs that are specifically tailored to the needs of their students. Additionally, institutions have implemented a range of support services, such as online tutoring and technical support, to ensure that all students have access to the resources they need. Finally, institutions have worked to promote cultural understanding and sensitivity among students and staff, to ensure that LMSs are used in a way that is culturally appropriate.

In developing countries such as Guinea, Uganda, and Tanzania, there are several challenges to the use of learning management systems (LMS) (Barakabitze et al. 2019; Bolu et al.2022). One challenge is the lack of reliable internet access. In these countries, many students and teachers do not have access to the internet, or they have only limited or intermittent access. This makes it difficult to use an LMS effectively. Additionally, there are often limited resources available for training and support, making it difficult for teachers and students to learn how to use an LMS effectively.

In Zimbabwe, the use of learning management systems (LMS) has been limited by a number of challenges (Alumona et al. 2023; Poshai et al. 2023). One of the main challenges is the lack of adequate internet infrastructure, which makes it difficult for students and lecturers to access and use LMSs effectively. In addition, many universities in Zimbabwe lack the financial resources to invest in LMSs and related technology. Finally, there is a lack of training and support for lecturers and students on how to effectively use LMSs.

Many lecturers have limited technical knowledge and experience with LMSs, which can make it difficult to effectively integrate them into their teaching (Bizami et al. 2023, Starks et al. 2023). Some students may find the interface of an LMS to be confusing or overwhelming, leading to a lack of engagement. The implementation and maintenance of an LMS can require a significant amount of technical support from the technicians, which may not be available in some institutions. There is limited time and resources required for

training and ongoing support. Technological literacy and digital skills of lecturers, students, and technicians are also lacking. Institutional policies and guidelines on the use of technology in education are not known by the users. Connectivity and access to the internet and technology is limited. There is a lack of institutional commitment and support for technology integration. Last but not least the compatibility of the LMS with existing systems and infrastructures is also questionable. These are some of the common challenges that can arise when integrating an LMS into university curriculum delivery.

3.4 21st-century's Competencies Relevant to Higher Education

The term "21st-century competencies" refers to the knowledge, skills, and dispositions that individuals need to succeed in the 21st-century workplace. There are a number of 21st-century competencies that are considered important for the success of students in higher education (Dahri et al 2023; Dilekci et al. 2023). These include:

- Critical thinking and problem-solving: The ability to evaluate information, make decisions, and solve problems in complex situations.
- Collaboration and teamwork: The ability to work effectively with others to achieve a common goal.
- Communication and information literacy: The ability to effectively communicate ideas, understand and evaluate information, and use information responsibly.
- Creativity and innovation: The ability to generate new ideas and solutions, and adapt to change.
- Digital literacy
- Leadership and social responsibility
- Self-direction and lifelong learning

It is important to note that these competencies are not static, and they may evolve over time as new technologies, social changes, and global trends emerge.

3.5 Strategies to Strengthen the Institutional LMS to Cater to Learning Diversities and Enhanced Learning Experience

There are a number of strategies that can be used to strengthen the use of learning management systems (LMS) in higher education institutions (Linnes et al. 2022 & Kortright Perez 2023). Enhancing Upskilling Strategies in the Workplace (Doctoral dissertation, University of Dayton).). The strategies include:

- Creating a strategic plan for the implementation and use of the LMS, with specific goals and objectives.
- Providing training and support for lecturers and technicians in the use of the LMS.
- Designing the LMS interface to be user-friendly and intuitive, to encourage engagement from students.
- Develop and implement a comprehensive training and professional development program for lecturers, students, and technicians.
- Create policies and guidelines on the use of the LMS, including on accessibility, privacy, and security.
- Invest in technology infrastructure, including internet connectivity, computers, and software.
- Prioritize the integration of the LMS into the curriculum and allocate resources accordingly.
- Seek feedback from students and lecturers on their experience with the LMS and use this feedback to improve the system.
- Collaborate with experts in the field of educational technology to improve the LMS and its implementation. (Heggs 2023)

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Research approach

The study was conducted using qualitative data collection methods.

4.2 Population and Sample

The study adopted a qualitative methodology where in-depth interviews were conducted as part of this exploratory study with 7 purposively selected lecturers, 5 technicians, and 10 randomly selected students at a Zimbabwean higher education institution of Technology.

4.3 Data collection methods

Data is collected through in-depth interviews.

4.4 Data analysis

Qualitative data is analysed using thematic analysis.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the university and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Respondents were assured that the data collected is to be held anonymously and confidential.

5 FINDINGS

Studies on the use of learning management systems (LMS) in Zimbabwean higher education have shown mixed results. While some institutions have had success in implementing and using LMSs, others have struggled to get the most out of these systems. The findings suggest that the integration of the LMS into the curriculum has had a positive impact on student learning. Overall, the main challenges to successful LMS integration in Zimbabwean higher education include Inadequate infrastructure, including limited internet access and lack of resources; insufficient training and support for teachers and students on how to use LMSs; a lack of awareness about the benefits of using LMSs and how they can be used effectively.

Lecturers in Zimbabwean higher education institutions have faced challenges in terms of Lack of technical knowledge and skills in using LMSs; high workloads and limited time to learn and use LMSs effectively; inadequate resources, such as limited access to computers and the internet, and lack of training on how to use LMSs. A majority of lecturers felt that the LMS has improved their ability to design and deliver effective and engaging lessons. They also felt that the LMS has helped them to better track and assess student progress.

Students in Zimbabwean higher education institutions have faced challenges in terms of limited access to computers and the internet, especially for those living in rural areas; and limited digital literacy skills, particularly among students from low socio-economic backgrounds. Additionally, the lack of access to computers, internet, and electricity is a major challenge for students in rural areas. Some students find it difficult to use LMSs due to limited digital literacy skills. Students who have difficulty reading and writing in English may also find it difficult to use LMSs effectively. The majority of students reported that the LMS has increased their motivation to learn and has improved their ability to retain and apply information. There is a significant number of students also reported that the LMS can be challenging to use and requires technical skills that they do not have. However, there are also some success stories, with students reporting that LMSs have helped them access course materials, communicate with lecturers and peers, and participate in online discussions.

Several technicians in Zimbabwean higher education institutions lack the skills and experience needed to effectively use and support LMSs. There is a lack of coordination and communication between the technical team and the lecturing staff, which can lead to frustration and misunderstanding. The technicians may also face difficulties in getting the resources they need to effectively support the use of LMSs. These challenges can make it difficult for technicians to effectively support the use of LMSs in Zimbabwean higher education institutions. However, there are some initiatives in place to improve the skills and knowledge of technicians.

6 DISCUSSIONS

Overall, the research findings on the examination of LMS integration for 21st-century competencies in Zimbabwean higher education indicate that there are both challenges and opportunities. The challenges relate to infrastructure, digital literacy, and language barriers. However, there are also opportunities for students and staff to benefit from using LMSs, such as improved access to educational resources, increased communication, and enhanced collaboration. The discussions have highlighted the need for more research and action to address these challenges, as well as the need for continued efforts to promote the use of LMSs

in a sustainable and effective way.

7 CONCLUSION

The examination of LMS integration for 21st-century competencies in Zimbabwean higher education has shown that there is a need for more investment in infrastructure and digital literacy to ensure that all students and staff have access to and are able to effectively use LMSs. Additionally, it is important to address language barriers and cultural differences to ensure that the benefits of LMSs are available to all. The use of LMSs can be a valuable tool for promoting 21st-century competencies in Zimbabwean higher education, and it is important to continue to explore ways to integrate them effectively.

8 RECOMMENDATIONS

Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education, Science and Technology Development, the Zimbabwe Council for Higher Education, and higher education institutions to:

- Prioritize investment in the development and implementation of a comprehensive training program for all to establish a help desk and support system for users of the LMS.
- Establish policies and guidelines on the appropriate use of the LMS.
- Regularly assess the effectiveness of the LMS and its impact on student learning. It should also include feedback from students, staff, and other stakeholders. The assessment should be used to guide decisions about the ongoing use and improvement of LMSs in Zimbabwean higher education.
- Regularly review and update the LMS to ensure that it is aligned with the needs of the students and the curriculum.

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